

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**PREVELANCE OF DAWN PHENOMENON AND SOMOGYI
EFFECT IN DIABETIC PATIENTS**¹Dr. Adnan Sharif, ²Dr. Hasan Amin, ³Dr. Masooma Batool Ghauri¹Mohtarma Benazir Bhutto Shaheed Medical College, Mirpur AJK²Ibn-e-Siena Hospital & Research Institute, Multan³Sargodha Medical College, Sargodha**Abstract:**

Patient with diabetes mellitus may have morning hyperglycemia despite of management due to somogyi effect and dawn phenomenon. Occurrence of dawn phenomenon is due to relative deficiency of insulin during the night time when insulin antagonist hormones are rising, so patient experience morning hyperglycemia and hypoglycemia at midnight as well. Somogyi effect occurs due to relative insulin excess which causes midnight hypoglycemia and subsequent morning hyperglycemia due to effects of reactionary raised insulin antagonizing hormones. In this study, 41(21%) out of 200 selected diabetic patients were having morning hypoglycemia despite of insulin therapy. 8(19%) were experiencing it due to somogyi effect and remaining 34(81%) due to dawn phenomenon. Strict glycemic control is essential to prevent complications of diabetes mellitus. Hence, these morning hyperglycemic patients must be screened and their insulin regimen adjusted accordingly.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Adnan Sharif,**Mohtarma Benazir Bhutto Shaheed Medical College,
Mirpur AJK

QR code

Please cite this article in press Adnan Sharif et al., **Prevelance of Dawn Phenomenon and Somogyi Effect in Diabetic Patients.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Diabetic patients taking insulin for glycemic control may have morning hyperglycemia. It can be due to two possible reasons: 1. dawn phenomenon 2. Somogyi effect

The dawn phenomenon occurs when endogenous insulin secretion decreases or when the effect of the exogenous insulin administered to the patient at the previous evening disappears, together with a physiological increase in insulin-antagonistic hormones. The dawn phenomenon is more common than the Somogyi effect.

Somogyi effect occurs in a person if he administer more than required insulin or doesn't eat a regular bedtime snack, and the person's blood sugar level drops during the night. As a response to that hypoglycemia the person's body responds by releasing hormones (cortisol, glucagon and growth hormone) that raise the blood sugar level.

Dawn phenomenon**Definition and pathogenesis**

Recurring abnormally high plasma glucose levels in the morning before breakfast are commonly called the dawn phenomenon. According to the daily insulin secretion profile [1], the dawn phenomenon can be divided into two types: physiological and pathological. Both types occur at the same time of the day but differ in the value of plasma glucose levels. The physiological dawn phenomenon is associated with a natural decrease of insulin secretion at midnight combined with elevation of blood glucose level remaining up to standard. This decrease of insulin secretion unblocks the secretion of insulin-antagonistic hormones with hyperglycaemic properties, particularly GH. The morning plasma glucose level growth in non-diabetic people with undisturbed insulin secretion is compensated by an additional burst of insulin. In turn, diabetic patients may experience the pathological dawn phenomenon, where the morning plasma glucose level is abnormally high due to insulin secretion disturbances plus the effects of nocturnal GH secretion [2].

The dawn phenomenon is a combination of an initial decrease in insulin requirement followed by an increase in the insulin needs [3]. Therefore, the dawn phenomenon can occur among both people with type 1 and type 2 diabetes mellitus with deterioration of beta cells function and without insulin therapy [4-6]. The decrease of endogenous insulin causes the lack of sufficient repression of insulin antagonistic hormones secretion, mainly GH [7], cortisol and

catecholamines [8] and leads to hyperglycaemia. Because of the impaired function of pancreatic beta cells, there is also an insufficient insulin secretion in response to hyperglycaemia which causes long-acting hyperglycaemia, detected by patients after awakening as the dawn phenomenon. Likewise, the dawn phenomenon occurs when the action of exogenous insulin administered to the patient the previous day is running out, and at the same time overlapping physiological growth of insulin-antagonistic hormones is observed. There is also the phenomenon called 'extended dawn phenomenon' [9]. This is seen when the high morning glucose level remains high until mid-morning. The cause of extended dawn phenomenon can be too many carbohydrates in the breakfast meal, or the pathologically extended stage of growth hormone secretion which is not repressed by hyperglycaemia, seen more often among diabetic patients [10].

The Somogyi effect**Definition and pathogenesis**

Although the existence and pathogenesis of the dawn phenomenon are indisputable in scientific society, the Somogyi effect is still a matter of debate. The name of the phenomenon derives from the surname of Austro-Hungarian scientist Michael Somogyi. In 1949, during the ACS meeting in Atlantic City, he made a speech about insulin's influence on diabetic patients. On the basis of his investigations, he concluded that people who had been given too large doses of insulin became "actually victims of chronic insulin poisoning" [11]. In his paper entitled: "Exacerbation of diabetes by excess insulin action", Somogyi developed his initial statement by adding a conclusion that too much insulin led through hypoglycaemia to hyperglycaemia [12]. Moreover, Somogyi created a hypothesis that hyperglycaemia after hypoglycaemia is a result of the insulin-antagonistic action of some hormones, especially those belonging to the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis [12]. The risk of occurrence of the Somogyi effect is also increased by using NPH insulin in diabetes therapy, which can be connected with the evident peak of its concentration taking place 4-5 hours after evening injection and its intermediate duration of action (10-16 hours) [13]. According to Raskin [14], asymptomatic nocturnal hypoglycaemia is common, but subsequent fasting hyperglycaemia is not necessarily the result of "rebound", because the present therapeutic regimen of NPH/Lente insulin given at supertime cause over night hyperinsulinaemia. Excessive fasting hyperglycaemia rarely follows nocturnal hypoglycaemia, except when excessive glucose is ingested to correct hyperglycaemia [3]. Moreover,

nocturnal hypoglycaemia correlates with falling plasma insulin levels rather than with increasing concentrations of counter regulatory hormones, whose secretion is often disturbed [14]. Such deterioration in insulin-antagonistic hormone levels during asymptomatic nocturnal hypoglycaemia was proved by Jones et al. [15] in a group of patients with type 1 diabetes and without diabetes. Among patients with diabetes, plasma epinephrine and norepinephrine responses to hypoglycaemia were blunted or reduced when they were asleep. The patients' plasma cortisol concentrations did not increase, while GH concentrations increased slightly. This defective glucose counter regulation is associated with substantially increased rates of severe iatrogenic hypoglycaemia in people with type 1 diabetes [16].

Somogyi's hypothesis has been tested by numerous scientists, who have accepted or rejected its existence. Research supporting the existence of the Somogyi effect includes the experiment carried out by Matyka et al. [17]. Their study involved two groups of 29 type 1 diabetic and non-diabetic children. The aim of the study was to determine the response of insulin-antagonistic hormones to hypoglycaemia. The results revealed a small increase of plasma GH and a rise of plasma epinephrine during nightly hypoglycaemia compared to a night without hypoglycaemia. The levels of norepinephrine, cortisol and glucagon were the same after a night without hypoglycaemia. Furthermore, the above-mentioned study found a significant increase in plasma insulin concentration between 11 p.m. and 3 a.m. among type 1 diabetic children, but not in non-diabetic children [17]. Perriello et al. [18] showed that fasting and post-breakfast plasma glucose levels were significantly higher after nocturnal hypoglycaemia than when hypoglycaemia was prevented. Moreover, fasting levels of plasma glucose in their study correlated directly with overnight plasma levels of epinephrine, GH and cortisol. Bolli et al. [19] drew similar conclusions, and indicated that hypoglycaemia can cause rebound hyperglycaemia in the absence of insulin waning in patients with type 1 diabetes, and that this results primarily from an excessive increase in glucose production due to activation of glucose counter regulatory systems. In another study [20], the authors observed the presence of the relationship between the Somogyi effect and the exuberant counter regulatory release of GH caused by nocturnal hypoglycaemia among patients with type 1 diabetes.

Tordjman et al. [21] assessed whether nocturnal hypoglycaemia actually caused morning

hyperglycaemia among type 1 diabetic patients. Their results contradict the existence of the Somogyi effect, as the presence of nightly hypoglycaemia was not followed by the development of morning hyperglycaemia. Moreover, the morning plasma glucose positively correlated with the nocturnal plasma glucose levels. Similar studies, but using CGMS, conducted by Guillod et al. [22] and Høi-Hansen et al. [23], also proved that morning hyperglycaemia was not related to nightly hypoglycaemia. Furthermore, Monnier et al. [24] demonstrated that nocturnal hypoglycaemia resulted in hyperglycaemia the next day, if it was observed before noon, but not in the early morning, which is called 'mid-morning hyperglycaemia'. Somogyi's next hypothesis investigated by scientists was the relationship between morning hyperglycaemia and the levels of hormones with antagonistic action to insulin as a result of nightly hypoglycaemia. Gale et al. [25] examined two groups of 15 patients with and without episodes of nocturnal hypoglycaemia for increased plasma level of GH, cortisol and glucagon during the morning hyperglycaemia. The results showed no increase in insulin-antagonistic hormone levels among patients with hyperglycaemia and a negative correlation between the plasma glucose concentration and the plasma free insulin concentration. This proves that during morning hyperglycaemia, a decrease in plasma insulin levels is observed. This suggests that hyperglycaemia may be the result of insulin dropping late at night, rather than an increase of insulin-antagonistic hormones. Similar conclusions were drawn also by Fowelin et al. [10] and Hirsch et al. [26]. According to above-cited data; the existence of the Somogyi effect has not been definitively proven. However, science supposes it to exist, and it is supposed to be present in clinical practice among large number of patients with morning hyperglycaemia. With regard to the impact of the excessive dose of insulin on the Somogyi effect, it is highly probable that this phenomenon can occur not only among patients with type 1 diabetes, but also among patients with type 2 and secondary types of diabetes, provided patients have been intensively treated with insulin the nocturnal plasma glucose levels. Similar studies, but using CGMS, conducted by Guillod et al. [22] and Høi-Hansen et al. [23], also proved that morning hyperglycaemia was not related to nightly hypoglycaemia. Furthermore, Monnier et al. [24] demonstrated that nocturnal hypoglycaemia resulted in hyperglycaemia the next day, if it was observed before noon, but not in the early morning, which is called 'mid-morning hyperglycaemia'. Somogyi's next hypothesis investigated by scientists was the relationship between morning

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According to above-cited data, the existence of the Somogyi effect has not been definitively proven. However, science supposes it to exist, and it is supposed to be present in clinical practice among large number of patients with morning hyperglycaemia. With regard to the impact of the excessive dose of insulin on the Somogyi effect, it is highly probable that this phenomenon can occur not only among patients with type 1 diabetes, but also among patients with type 2 and secondary types of diabetes, provided patients have been intensively treated with insulin.

Objective of Study

This study was aimed at finding the prevalence of morning hyperglycemia in diabetic patients who were already on insulin therapy and categorize them between dawn phenomenon and somogyi effect.

Study Design

Cross sectional study

Sampling Size: 200 patients

Sampling Technique: Patients were selected by convenient sampling (simple random sampling)

Inclusion Criteria: Known diabetic patients of all age groups taking insulin therapy (at least from 1 month).

Exclusion Criteria: Diabetic patients on oral hypoglycemic.

Place and Duration: This study was conducted in North Medical Ward Mayo Hospital Lahore from May 2018 to July 2018

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

200 known diabetic patients admitted in medical ward were taken as sample by convenient sampling. Fasting blood glucose levels were checked for five consecutive mornings and midnight at 2am with digital glucometer.

Data Analysis: Data has been analyzed by using SPSS 20. Results will be described in percentage with pie charts.

RESULTS:

Among the sample of 200 patients 42 were found to have morning hyperglycemia and remaining 158 were euglycemic. 34(81%) out of 42 were having high blood glucose levels at 2:00am midnight while 8(19%) were having hypoglycemia at that time. Similar results were found in next mornings and midnights. Out of total 200 patients 34(17%) had morning hyperglycemia due to dawn phenomenon and 8(4% of total) had it because of somogyi effect

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

Both the dawn phenomenon and the Somogyi effect are associated with the development of morning hyperglycaemia, but the pathological mechanisms responsible for these effects are different.

Significant number (21%) of selected diabetic

patients were experiencing morning hyperglycemia despite of being on insulin therapy. 34(81%) were having it due to Dawn phenomenon. Remaining 8(19%) had it due somogyi effect. The dawn phenomenon is more common than the Somogyi effect. Both types can be easily diagnosed and there

are some methods of treatment and prevention. The best way of preventing these phenomena is good diabetes mellitus control with appropriate insulin therapy. Strict glycemic control is required in diabetics to avoid complications.

Some possible prevention/treatment options for dawn phenomenon are:

1: *Increase evening physical activity*

2: *Increase amount of protein to carbohydrates in the last meal of the day*

3: *Long-acting insulin analogues like glargine instead of NPH insulin*

Similarly, to prevent/treat somogyi effect following measures could be taken:

1: *Do not miss dinner*

2: *More protein than carbohydrates in the last meal of the day*

3: *Modify(decrease) insulin dosage*

4: *Long-acting insulin analogues like glargine instead of NPH insulin*

5: *Go to bed with higher level of plasma glucose than usual*

As pathogenesis of these effects is complicated and still to be explored, further research is warranted which may help reduce dawn phenomenon and Somogyi effect.

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